

A New 4D Chaotic System Based on Memristor and Circuit Design

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This paper reports the development of a new 4-dimensional chaotic system by replacing the Non-Linear (NL) positive conductance of Shinriki's circuit with a memristor emulator. Then, we present on this topic the equilibrium point of the mathematical model describing our system and their stabilities, dissipative properties, Lyapunov Exponents (LE), Kaplan–Yorke (K.Y) dimensions as well as the bifurcation diagrams. In the end, the electrical circuit made on Multisim 14.2 software is given.

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1. Introduction

Due to their potential applications in different fields, such as secure communication [1–5], robotics [6], and encryption applications [7, 8], new chaotic systems and circuits arouse the interest of the scientific and research community. Lately, in order to the real needs imposed by these technologies, a great number of chaotic circuits have been discovered [9–11]. For this, many researchers have decided to obtain strange attractors with nonlinear algebraic structures as simple as possible and these systems are strongly recommended for electrical implementations [12, 13].

Three most relevant inventions that have been identified in evolution of this field of research are those of Professor Leon O. Chua: the Chua's circuit [14], Cellular Neural/Nonlinear Networks (CNN) [15–17] and memory resistance, which is known under the name of memristor.

Theoretically, the fundamental elements of

a circuit are three ones [18]: a resistor (R), an inductor (L), and a capacitor (C), which give the relationships between voltage and current, current and flux, and voltage and charge (resp.). In 1971, Chua notices the lack of relationship that connects charge and flow, which implies the possibility of the existence of an element that can couple them. So, Leon Chua carried out studies [19] and [20], of which he determined a novel passive element which he named memristor.

However, the memristor remains only a theory and does not arouse curiosity of scientists until its experimental accomplishment by Hewlett-Packard, the American computer hardware and software company during the last decades. It was not until 2008 that the first physical model of a memristor was made by Stan William and his group at the HP laboratory by inserting a layer of TiO_2 between two layers of Platinum [21], [22]. The Memristor is a nano-device that is characterized by a unique set of “fingerprints” and a number of ways to

generate superior circuitry properties, as well as: a pinched-hysteresis (V-I) relationship, a correlation between signal amplitude and applied frequency, and non-volatile characteristics.

Compared to standard memory technologies, the memristor is distinguished by several characteristics: good scalability, untimely, no leakage current with high density as well as a speed of one DRAM. Because of these advantages, researchers have thought of several uses of the memristor in classical circuits. Nevertheless, due to the difficulties of manufacturing this new element, after studies, many researchers opted for the design of memristor emulators [23–28]. A wide variety of memristor practices can be found in the literature ranging from neuromorphic circuits [29], [30], to chaotic circuits [31, 32].

In recent times, scholars in the complexity science community have developed many chaotic systems [33–40]. They have been able to theorize memristor-based chaos oscillators with the substitution of a nonlinear or linear constituent by a memory resistor or memristive system [41]. Depended on Shinriki's circuit which is a modified Van der Pol oscillator, various works have been carried out by putting in place of an NL component or a resistor, a bridge of memory diodes [42–45].

In this work, which is established on interesting work built on the Shinriki's oscillator, a newly discovered chaotic system is suggested by replacing the NL positive conductance of the Shinriki's circuit by the memristor emulator given in [46] with adaptation of some variables. This new system is characterized by its complexity and its strong nonlinearity, moreover it contains several cryptographic keys, it also generates excellent chaotic signals and gives complex strange attractors which favors its exploitation in several applications based on chaos as well as the secure communications and transmissions.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. The modeling process of the new chaotic memristor is given in Section 2. In Section 3, some main properties of the model are detailed. In Section 4, the circuit implementation of the

new chaotic system is presented. At the end, in Section 5, conclusions and some proposals and considerations for future work are offered.

2. A new chaotic memristive system

In 1971, Leon Ch. hypothesized that the memristor is the fourth passive element that establishes the relationship between flux and charge. He defined the memristor with Kang as follows [20]:

$$\begin{cases} y = g(x, u, t)u, \\ \dot{x} = f(x, u, t) \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where u and y are the inputs and outputs of the system and x the internal state of the system, while the functions $f(\cdot)$ and $g(\cdot)$ are related to the particular memristor.

In order to obtain the new system, in this work we replaced the NL positive conductance of the Shinriki's circuit, which is given in Fig. 1, by the memristor emulator proposed in [46] which is introduced as:

$$\begin{cases} i_M(t) = -k_0 V_M(t) + k_1 \sigma^2(t) V_M(t) \\ \quad - k_2 \sigma^4(t) V_M(t), \\ \dot{\sigma}(t) = l[k_3 - k_4 \sigma^2(t) - k_5 \sigma^4(t) - k_6 V_M(t) \\ \quad - k_7 \sigma(t) V_M(t)] \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where i_M is the output and is the current that flows through the memristor, σ is the state variable of the memristor, $\frac{d\sigma}{dt}$ is the speed of motion, $l = 10^4$, and k_n are memristor unfolding parameters. These are defined as follows: $k_0 = 6$, $k_1 = -2$, $k_2 = -7$, $k_3 = -0.333$, $k_4 = -1.111$, $k_5 = 0.833$, $k_6 = 1$, $k_7 = 1.333$. The equivalent circuit which represents the latter is illustrated by Fig. 2.

The ($I - V$) characteristic curve of the memristor emulator is given in Fig. 3. We polarized our emulator with a sinusoidal signal of amplitude of 1 V with different frequencies namely 1 kHz, 1.3 kHz, 2 kHz and 5 kHz. We notice that all the pinched hysteresis loops

pass through the origin (0, 0). By increasing the frequency, from 5 kHz, the pinched hysteresis loop narrows in a straight line with a slope of 1 as shown in Fig. 3. Based on Kirchof's electric circuit, and using the memristor of the system (2), we obtained a new chaotic circuit described by the following equations:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{dv_1}{dt} = \frac{1}{C_1}[(\frac{1}{R_3} - \frac{1}{R_4})v_1 \\ + k_0(v_2 - v_1) + k_1\sigma^2(v_2 - v_1) + k_2\sigma^4(v_2 - v_1)], \\ \frac{dv_2}{dt} = \frac{1}{C_2}[-i_L - \frac{1}{R_5}v_2 \\ - k_0(v_2 - v_1) - k_1\sigma^2(v_2 - v_1) - k_2\sigma^4(v_2 - v_1)], \\ \frac{di_L}{dt} = \frac{1}{L}v_2, \\ \frac{d\sigma}{dt} = l[k_3 + k_4\sigma^2 + k_5\sigma^4 + k_6(v_2 - v_1) \\ + k_7\sigma(v_2 - v_1)]. \end{array} \right. \quad (3)$$

In order to perform an analytical and numerical change of variable is necessary:

$$\begin{aligned} x_1 &= \frac{v_1}{V_{ref}}, \quad x_2 = \frac{v_2}{V_{ref}}, \quad x_3 = \frac{i_L\sqrt{\frac{L}{C_2}}}{V_{ref}}, \quad x_4 = \frac{\sigma}{V_{ref}}, \\ t &= \tau\sqrt{LC_2}, \quad A_0 = (\frac{1}{R_3} - \frac{1}{R_4})\frac{1}{C_1}\sqrt{LC_2}, \\ A_1 &= k_0\frac{C_2}{C_1}\sqrt{\frac{L}{C_2}}, \quad A_2 = k_1\frac{C_2}{C_1}V_{ref}^2\sqrt{\frac{L}{C_2}}, \\ A_3 &= k_2\frac{C_2}{C_1}V_{ref}^4\sqrt{\frac{L}{C_2}}, \quad A_4 = \frac{1}{R_5C_2}\sqrt{LC_2}, \quad A_5 = \\ &k_0\sqrt{\frac{L}{C_2}}, \quad A_6 = k_1V_{ref}^2\sqrt{\frac{L}{C_2}}, \quad A_7 = k_2V_{ref}^4\sqrt{\frac{L}{C_2}}, \\ A_8 &= l\frac{k_3}{V_{ref}}\sqrt{LC_2}, \quad A_9 = lk_4V_{ref}\sqrt{LC_2}, \\ A_{10} &= lk_5V_{ref}^3\sqrt{LC_2}, \quad A_{11} = lk_6\sqrt{LC_2}, \\ A_{12} &= lk_7V_{ref}\sqrt{LC_2}. \end{aligned}$$

By performing this change of variables, we obtain a new fourth-order nonlinear system:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \dot{x}_1 = A_0x_1 + (A_1 + A_2x_4^2 + A_3x_4^4)(x_2 - x_1), \\ \dot{x}_2 = -x_3 - A_4x_2 - (A_5 + A_6x_4^2 + A_7x_4^4)(x_2 - x_1), \\ \dot{x}_3 = x_2, \\ \dot{x}_4 = A_8 + A_9x_4^2 + A_{10}x_4^4 + A_{11}(x_2 - x_1) \\ + A_{12}x_4(x_2 - x_1). \end{array} \right. \quad (4)$$

With the following initial conditions: $x(0) = [0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.04]^T$, and adjusting system (2) settings as follows: $A_0 = 0.9$, $A_1 = 0.1$, $A_2 = 2.2$, $A_3 = 590$, $A_4 = 0.0326$, $A_5 = 0.92$, $A_6 = 0.03$, $A_7 = 0.4$, $A_8 = 10^{-7}$, $A_9 = 0.0007$, $A_{10} = 0.0005$, $A_{11} = 0.07$, $A_{12} = 0.07$, we get a new chaotic

attractors which are represented by Fig. 4.

3. Analysis of the proposed chaotic memristive system

In order to examine the performance of a chaotic system, we use several techniques and in this work, in this section, to evaluate our system we will use: Equilibria and stability, LEs, Dimension and bifurcation, K.Y.

3.1. Equilibria and stability

To calculate the equilibrium points of the system (4) it suffices to solve the following equations:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} A_0x_1 + (A_1 + A_2x_4^2 + A_3x_4^4)(x_2 - x_1) = 0, \\ -x_3 - A_4x_2 - (A_5 + A_6x_4^2 + A_7x_4^4)(x_2 - x_1) = 0, \\ x_2 = 0 \\ A_8 + A_9x_4^2 + A_{10}x_4^4 + A_{11}(x_2 - x_1) \\ + A_{12}x_4(x_2 - x_1) = 0. \end{array} \right. \quad (5)$$

After solving the equations, the system has a single equilibrium point: $E = (0, 0, 0, 0)$. At this equilibrium point set, the Jacobi matrix $J(E)$ is:

$$J(E) = \begin{pmatrix} A_0 - A_1 & A_1 & 0 & 0 \\ A_5 & -A_4 - A_5 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ -A_{11} & A_{11} & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

The eigenvalues of $J(E)$ are calculated with MATLAB, and the values are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_1 &= 0, \\ \alpha_2 &= -0.4917 + 0.8492i, \\ \alpha_3 &= -0.4917 - 0.8492i, \\ \alpha_4 &= 0.8308. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

3.2. Lyapunov Exponents

Lyapunov Exponents is a mathematical tool used to define the long-term state of a system. The numerically calculated Lyapunov exponents

FIG. 1: Sketch presenting the original Shinriki's circuit.

FIG. 2: The equivalent circuit of the emulator defined by the system of equations (2).

of our system are:

$$\lambda_1 = 0.047028, \lambda_2 = 0.004130, \lambda_3 = -0.003945, \lambda_4 = -3.234001.$$

Fig. 5 illustrates the Lyapunov exponents of system which are calculated by Wolf's algorithm [47] with the following parameter values: $A_0 = 0.9$,

$$A_1 = 0.1, A_2 = 2.2, A_3 = 590, A_4 = 0.0326, A_5 = 0.92, A_6 = 0.03, A_7 = 0.4, A_8 = 10^{-7}, A_9 = 0.0007, A_{10} = 0.0005, A_{11} = 0.07, A_{12} = 0.07.$$

The corresponding four Lyapunov exponents are:

FIG. 3. Characteristics associated with (V_m, I_m) plotted for amplitude $A = 1$ V at different frequencies: (a) $f = 1$ kHz, (b) $f = 1.3$ kHz, (c) $f = 2$ kHz, (d) $f = 5$ kHz.

FIG. 4: The chaotic attractors obtained on MATLAB with the initial conditions $x(0) = [0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.04]^T$.

$$D_L = \sigma + \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{\sigma} \lambda_i}{|\lambda_{\sigma+1}|} = 3 + \frac{\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \lambda_3}{|\lambda_4|} = 3.01459,$$

where σ is defined by $\sum_{i=1}^{\sigma} \lambda_i$ and $\sum_{i=1}^{\sigma+1} \lambda_i < 0$. From this result, we notice that a Lyapunov dimension is fractional and that the chaotic attractors with 2 positive LEs. This illustrates that the propose system is hyperchaotic one.

3.3. Bifurcation

To can study the dynamic of systems, a mathematical tool is used, it is the bifurcation diagram. It illustrates the asymptotic values (fixed points, periodic points, chaotic attractors).

To illustrate the road to chaos, the system (4) parameters are adjusted as follows: $A_1 =$

FIG. 5. Lyapunov exponents for the system (4) with the following parameter values: $A_0 = 0.9$, $A_1 = 0.1$, $A_2 = 2.2$, $A_3 = 590$, $A_4 = 0.0326$, $A_5 = 0.92$, $A_6 = 0.03$, $A_7 = 0.4$, $A_8 = 10^{-7}$, $A_9 = 0.0007$, $A_{10} = 0.0005$, $A_{11} = 0.07$, $A_{12} = 0.07$.

FIG. 6. The bifurcation diagrams with the variation of: (a) A_0 from 0.08 to 2. (b) A_{11} from 0.06 to 1. (c) A_6 from 0.01 to 5.

FIG. 8. (Color online) The chaotic attractors obtained with Multisim in the following planes: $x_2 - x_1$ (a), $x_1 - x_4$ (b), $x_2 - x_4$ (c), $x_2 - x_3$ (d).

We find that $A_0 - A_1 - A_4 - A_5 < 0$ proves that the system is dissipative and the system may have chaotic attractors. Also note the asymmetry of spaces and planes which increases the complexity of the system.

The dissipativeness can be confirmed with the Lyapunov exponents, according to Kolade, Atangana and Tarasov [48], if the sum of all the exponents is negative it confirms the dissipativeness of the system (4) and converges to the equilibrium point.

$$\sum_{i=1}^4 L_i = -3.186788 < 0. \quad (8)$$

4. Circuit realization

The analog circuit that corresponds to the system (4) is formed of four channels that accomplished mathematical operations namely multiplication, addition and integration of the 4 states of the system. This circuit was made on Multisim 14.2, it includes 25 linear resistors, 8 LM741CN operational amplifiers, 4 capacitors, a direct current source, and 633 CE analog multipliers. The latter is represented by the Fig.7. By applying Kirchhoff's law to the circuit of Fig.7, we obtain the following mathematical equations

which correspond to system (4):

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{dx_1}{dt} = \frac{1}{R_1 C_1} x_1 + \frac{1}{R_2 C_1} (x_2 - x_1) \\ \quad + \frac{1}{R_3 C_1} x_4^2 (x_2 - x_1) + \frac{1}{R_4 C_1} x_4^4 (x_2 - x_1), \\ \frac{dx_2}{dt} = -\frac{1}{R_5 C_2} x_3 - \frac{1}{R_6 C_2} x_2 - \frac{1}{R_7 C_2} (x_2 - x_1) \\ \quad - \frac{1}{R_8 C_2} x_4^2 (x_2 - x_1) - \frac{1}{R_9 C_2} x_4^4 (x_2 - x_1), \\ \frac{dx_3}{dt} = \frac{1}{R_{10} C_3} x_2, \\ \frac{dx_4}{dt} = \frac{V_n}{R_{11} C_4} + \frac{1}{R_{12} C_4} x_4^2 + \frac{1}{R_{13} C_4} x_4^4 \\ \quad + \frac{1}{R_{14} C_4} (x_2 - x_1) + \frac{1}{R_{15} C_4} x_4 (x_2 - x_1) \end{array} \right. \quad (9)$$

where $R_1 = 0.12 \text{ M}\Omega$, $R_2 = 1 \text{ M}\Omega$, $R_3 = 44 \text{ k}\Omega$, $R_4 = 169\Omega$, $R_5 = 100 \text{ k}\Omega$, $R_6 = 3.344 \text{ M}\Omega$, $R_7 = 108.6 \text{ k}\Omega$, $R_8 = 3.3 \text{ M}\Omega$, $R_9 = 250 \text{ k}\Omega$, $R_{10} = R_{11} = 100 \text{ k}\Omega$, $R_{12} = 181 \text{ M}\Omega$, $R_{13} = 200 \text{ M}\Omega$, $R_{14} = R_{15} = 1.42 \text{ M}\Omega$, $R_{16} = R_{17} = R_{18} = R_{19} = R_{20} = R_{21} = R_{22} = R_{23} = R_{24} = R_{25} = 10 \text{ k}\Omega$, $C_1 = C_2 = C_3 = C_4 = 10 \text{ nF}$, and the physical time $RC = 1\text{ms}$. Fig. 7 represents the electronic circuit in Multisim. Note that the phase

portraits obtained are illustrated by the Fig. 8.

5. Conclusion

In this article, to create this new chaotic system, we based ourselves on the Shinriki's oscillator which is the modified Van der Pol oscillator and a memristor emulator. The dynamical properties of the system were analyzed, such as equilibrium, stability, dissipation, Lyapunov exponents, Kaplan–Yorke dimension and bifurcation diagrams. By realizing the circuit on Multisim, we obtained strange attractors identical to those found with Matlab. This new system is characterized by its strong non-linearity as well as its richness in key which makes it potentially interesting in the field of cryptography as well as secure transmissions.

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